

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN PEDAGOGY AND ITS TYPES IN PERSONALITY FORMATION

Khalikulova Chinora

2nd year student of majoring in pedagogy and psychology,
Faculty of Pedagogy

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

Scientific supervisor: Turdieva Luiza Artikovna

Teacher at the Russian language department

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728330>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23th February 2024

Accepted: 26th February 2024

Published: 28th February 2024

KEYWORDS

*analysis, method, research,
psychology, pedagogy*

ABSTRACT

this article examines the features of the development of psychology and its impact on the pedagogical activities of teachers. A cross-sectional and comparative analysis of the influence of the choice of student assessment system in the development of their personal qualities was carried out. Recommendations are given for the implementation of developments in the study of student psychology.

Despite all the diversity of real life, each person remains himself, retains individual mental qualities in a combination that is unique to him. Therefore, one of the principles is the principle of analytical-synthetic or complex study of personality. Analytical study makes it possible to understand the elements of the psyche in various conditions of life and activity of the individual (comprehensively), and synthetic study makes it possible to identify the interrelationship of individual mental manifestations and find what is stable that characterizes a given person as a whole.

Pedagogy is a developing science; it constantly revises and refines aspects of understanding its main categories, and in practice it is continuously enriched by the experience of education and training. Every person is obliged to master the basics of pedagogical culture as a component of general culture.

The main tasks of psychology include: studying the mechanisms, patterns and qualitative features of the manifestation and development of mental processes, states and properties as reflective activity of the brain, studying the nature and conditions for the formation of mental characteristics of the individual and, on the basis of this, learning to manage these mental phenomena.

A teacher is involved in the upbringing and training of a person from childhood. The subject of pedagogy is the indivisible learning process, focused on the development and formation of personality in the conditions of education. The object of pedagogy is education, which is a purposeful and conscious process. These are those parts of reality that are a condition for the development of the human individual as a part of society. The outstanding Czech thinker, theologian, writer, teacher and founder of scientific pedagogy J. A. Komensky said that this

profession is honorable and respected, and therefore let only the best of people be teachers. Speaking about the role of the teacher and his influence on the individual, we must not forget about such a concept as pedagogical quality. This is a set of characteristics that describe the specifics of the teaching profession against the background of other professional fields of activity. It includes an attitude towards educational and professional activities, fluency in the subject of teaching. It is also skillful mastery of techniques and methods that help to effectively carry out training and education, resulting in a productive product. The famous Soviet teacher A. Sukhomlinsky, the founder of humanistic pedagogy, believed that the teaching profession is close to research activities.

The teacher must foresee the consequences of educational influence, analyze the facts, otherwise he will cease to be a creator. Without love for children, understanding their feelings, the joy of communicating with them, knowledge of your subject, knowledge in the fields of pedagogy and psychology, you cannot become a good teacher. It is important for a teacher to understand that his profession is not just a job, but also a mission of nurturing the individual. As we know, from age periodization, the leading activity of a school-age child is study, and he perceives it as responsibly as an adult does his work. And at this age, the child's attitude towards school in general and work subsequently is formed. Therefore, the role of the teacher, at this age, is as important as the parent's. It is what the teacher presents and how he does it that will influence the future personality of a person as a part of society. Personality is often defined as a social component consisting of acquired qualities. It is acquired in the sociocultural environment in the process of joint activity and communication. Closely related to this concept are stable properties that are responsible for a person's individuality. These are socio-psychological characteristics, the nature of which is stable, they include such components as: moral views, abilities, motivation, character, volitional qualities, attitudes and others.

The structure of human mental activity contains three interconnected aspects: cognitive, emotional and volitional. As a result of cognitive activity (including sensations, perception, memory, thinking, speech, imagination, attention) knowledge about the surrounding reality is formed. Emotional manifestations express an attitude towards what a person learns and does. Will provides an active influence on the environment and acts as a regulating function of human behavior. This means that a mental phenomenon is the unity of cognition, attitude and action. The need to pass on experience from generation to generation appeared at the very early stage of the emergence of human society. Therefore, the practice of education was originally defined as the transfer of a person's life experience from the older generation to the younger. Education was the same social phenomenon as any human activity: hunting, gathering, making tools. As a person grows as an individual and his social experience becomes more complex, the process and goals of education become more complex.

The first pedagogical knowledge existed orally and was passed on from generation to generation in the form of customs, traditions, games, commandments, fairy tales, wise advice, and lullabies. It was folk pedagogy, which was created by the most experienced, observant, wise representatives of the people. The origins of folk pedagogy as the first stage in the development of pedagogy can still be found today in songs, ditties, epics, fairy tales, proverbs and sayings, riddles, and folk signs. Then the most important pedagogical knowledge was immortalized in rock paintings, on roadside stones and the ceilings of huts, and, finally, with the development of writing, in books.

Pedagogy developed along with the development of society, was implemented in various forms of education and training of children, youth, and adults. Already in primitive society, educational relations arose to transfer the experience of generations and assimilate it. Pedagogy is connected with economics, solving problems of the economics of education and the organization of economic education of modern people. The relationship between pedagogy and psychology is already traditional. The results of psychological research, embodied in the laws of human mental development, allow teachers to organize the processes of teaching and education based on these laws. The forms of communication between pedagogy and other sciences are very diverse: this is the borrowing of scientific ideas (for example, the cybernetic model of control), the use of data obtained by other sciences (physiological data on the performance of students), etc.

Modern pedagogy is characterized by interaction with various natural and human sciences, but the influence of philosophy, psychology and anthropology remains dominant. It should be noted that pedagogy uses materials and data from related sciences not through mechanical transfer, but on the basis of strict selection with a mandatory analysis of the conditions and boundaries of their applicability in pedagogy.

With the accumulation of scientific knowledge and its specialization, differentiation took place within pedagogy: new branches were separated from general science, acquiring the status of independent pedagogical sciences. Depending on the objects of training and education in pedagogical science, three groups of branches are distinguished: special, age and professional. Within each branch, a group of separate pedagogical disciplines is distinguished.

Pedagogy is a developing science; it constantly revises and refines aspects of understanding its main categories, and in practice it is continuously enriched by the experience of education and training. Every person is obliged to master the basics of pedagogical culture as a component of general culture.

Do not forget that a person learns throughout his life - from birth to old age. On the basis of modern pedagogy and its branches, specialists from all branches of production and management personnel are trained and retrained. In addition, pedagogical knowledge can be useful to a modern person who interacts with other people in a variety of conditions. In general, knowledge of the basics of pedagogy will be useful to those who themselves strive to become a well-mannered and educated person and have a desire to help other people in this complex process.

References:

1. Salieva, Z. Z. (2018). Reading comprehension and comprehension strategies. *Учёный XXI века. Международный научный журнал*, (7-1), 42.
2. Salieva, Z. Z. (2024). DISTRACTERS OF MOTIVATION IN PRODUCING A WRITTEN TEXT OF STUDENTS IN EFL CLASSROOM. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 3(4 SPECIAL), 599-602.
3. Salieva, Z. (2023). SOME CHALLENGES FACED BY EFL STUDENTS ON WRITING SKILL. *UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH*, 1(7), 69-75.

4. Салиева, З. З. (2023). YOZISHNI ORQITISHNING XUSUSIYATLARI VA YONDASHUVLARI. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 6(3).
5. Гулрух, С. (2022). ВО 'LAJAK BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFI O 'QITUVCHILARINI IJODIY FAOLIYATNI TASHKIL ETISHGA TAYYORLASH PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA: Saidova Gulruh Halim qizi, Nizomiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (1), 208-214.
6. Qizi, S. G. H., & Qizi, H. H. H. (2023). TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING "4K" KOMPETENSIYALARI: KREATIVLIK, TANQIDIY FIKRLASH, KOMMUNIKATSIYA, KOOPERATSIYA. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 12), 430-432.
7. Saidova, G. (2020). CREATIVE CLASSES AS A MEANS OF FORMING PERSONAL AND COMPETENCY-BASED QUALITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PRIMARY CLASSES. In *ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ* (pp. 20-23).
8. Saidova, G. (2020). ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF THE TEACHER OF PRIMARY CLASSROOM IN THE PERIOD OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 86-90).
9. Gulchexra, K. (2023). FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(03), 40-44.
10. Кахарова, Д. С. БЎЛАЖАК ЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER Саидова Гулрух Халим қизи.
11. Ostonovich, B. O., & Khudayberdievich, S. H. (2023). Linguistic Analysis of Knowledge Issues in Psychological Discourse. *Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan*, 1(5), 355-369.
12. Bobokalonov, O. (2023). FRENCH SHIFONEMAS IN PHRASEOLOGICAL CONSTRUCTION ON HISTORICAL SOURCES. *АКТА NUUz (O'zMU Xabarlari)*.
13. Bobokalonov, O. (2023). Les phytophraséologismes ou phytophrasèmes. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 31(31).
14. Aripova, S. (2024). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 98-101.
15. Tohirovna, A. S. (2023). ENHANCING INDEPENDENT LEARNING STRATEGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH CASE STUDIES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(11), 651-652.
16. Aripova, S. T. (2023). INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA TALABALARNING IJODIY MUSTAQILLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 259-263.

17. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 7(1), 118-123.
18. Taxirovna, A. S. (2023). Lingua-cultural aspects of the translation of English and Uzbek stories. *Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany)*, 536-540.
19. Aripova, S. (2023). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS. *Science and innovation*, 2(C12), 37-42.
20. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS, SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI.
21. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2024). Objective Factors Affecting Uzbekistan's Access To The Bologna Agreement. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 29, 16-19.
22. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2024). THE INFLUENCE OF THE BOLOGNA PROCESS ON YOUTH'S WORLDVIEW. *Confrencea*, 1(1), 270-274.
23. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2023). Issues of Spiritual and Moral Education of the Mature Generation in Independent Uzbekistan. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(3S), 3864-3873.
24. Moydinova, E. (2021). THE ROLE OF MODERN ENGLISH TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGE OF DIGITALIZATION. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
25. Moydinova, E. (2022). INGLIZ TILINI O 'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
26. Moydinova, E. (2022). UNIVERSAL MASOFAVIY TA'LIM SHAROITIDA VEB-KVEST TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISHNING SAMARADORLIGI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
27. Odinaxon, I. (2023). TURLI TIZIMLI TILLARDA TARJIMON MAHORATI. *UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE*, 1(4), 27-32.
28. Ismanova, O. (2023). NEMIS VA OZBEK TILLAR KESIMIDA TARJIMONNING TARJIMADA LEKSIK SINONIMLARDAN TANLAB FOYDALANISH USLUBLARI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11 Part 2), 157-160.
29. Axrorova, R. U., Urunbayevna, I. O., & Ibrohimjon oqli, Q. A. (2022). XORIJIY TILLARNI OQITISHDA HAR BIR OQUVCHI BILAN INDIVIDUAL SHUGULLANISH VA KOPRIK TIL MOHIYATI. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(12), 22-24.
30. Кенжабаев, Ж. (2022). The implementation of literature in teaching speaking for advanced students. *Общество и инновации*, 3(2/S), 262-265.

- 31.** Kenjabaev, J. A. (2022). METHODS THROUGH THE INTERNET IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Экономика и социум*, (12-2 (103)), 67-70.
- 32.** Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). Communicative Language Teaching And The System Of Exercises. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 1017-1022.
- 33.** Кенжабаев, Ж. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ЭТАП РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ О ЯЗЫКЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (2 (105)), 704-707.
- 34.** Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH THROUGH INTERNET SITES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 3(11), 59-71.
- 35.** Kenjabayev, J. A. Linguistic features of the development of oral speech competence of students of the direction of physical culture education (on the example of sports terminology). *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences.-UK*, 11, 48-51.
- 36.** Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH THROUGH INTERNET SITES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 3(11), 59-71.
- 37.** Кенжабаев, Д. (2023). METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON INTERNET RESOURCES. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(11).
- 38.** Kenjabaev, J. A. (2024). Modern Teaching Methods in Teaching English. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 3(1), 52-56.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY